

Z-pin through-thickness enhancement of a composite laminates with variable thickness

Joël Serra, António R. Melro,

Giuliano Allegri, Stephen R. Hallett

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Outline

- **Multi-scale modelling framework**
- **From one delamination plane to several**
- **Verification cases**

Multi-scale modelling framework

Bridging data

Multi-scale modelling framework

From one delamination plane to several

- First step: Identify the proper bridging map

Z-pin length: $L = L^+ + L^-$

Z-pin asymmetry: $\alpha = \frac{\min(L^+, L^-)}{L^+ + L^-}$

Identifies the
bridging map
from the library

From one delamination plane to several

- Second step: Relate 'parallel' cohesive elements in different delamination planes

A link is established between 'parallel' cohesive elements

From one delamination plane to several

- Third step: Upon delamination propagation and cohesive element failure...

... the linked cohesive elements on the other delamination plane have their TTR geometrical properties **updated automatically.**

A different bridging map is called from the library for the surviving cohesive elements

Verification cases: Stepped DCB

Length: 80mm

Width: 1mm

Thickness: 8 -> 6mm

Verification cases: Stepped DCB

Verification cases: Curved Geometry

Variation of thickness in the two directions

3 delamination planes with reinforced areas

A voluntary complex geometry to test the algorithm.

Verification cases: Curved Geometry

Simulation time = 0s

Verification cases: Curved Geometry (I)

Mode I loading

Verification cases: Curved Geometry (I)

A delamination crack is propagating through the lower plane in Mode I.

Verification cases: Curved Geometry (II)

Verification cases: Curved Geometry (II)

A delamination crack is propagating through the mid-plane in Mode II.

Verification cases: ELS – 2 delaminations

Yasae, M., G. Mohamed, and S.R. Hallett, Interaction of Z-pins with Multiple Mode II Delaminations in Composite Laminates. *Experimental Mechanics*, 2016. 56(8): p. 1363-1372.

Verification cases: ELS – 2 delaminations

Verification cases: ELS – 2 delaminations

Conclusion and Future work

- **A multi-scale framework has been presented for the numerical modelling of composite laminates reinforced with z-pins**
- **« On the fly » Z-pin length and asymmetry are computed and updated if a cohesive interface « fails »**
- **The modelling of a composite laminate with several delaminations on different mode-mixities has been verified**

- **To fully validate, the code capabilities, experimental data will be compared to numerical predictions for several mixed-mode cracks propagating in a composite laminate**

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joel.serra@bristol.ac.uk